

DETERMINANTS OF ECONOMIC GROWTH IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This study applies the ARDL bounds testing approach of Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001) to analyse the determinants of Nigeria's economic growth from 1990 to 2023. Using real GDP *per capita* as the dependent variable, the model incorporates total trade, foreign direct investment (net inflows), gross fixed capital formation, and government recurrent spending on education. Results show that trade and education spending exert negative short-run effects, while FDI has a negative short-run but significant positive long-run impact. Gross fixed capital formation has a positive and significant effect on growth in the short run, but not in the long run. The error correction term confirms a stable long-run equilibrium, with 62% adjustment annually. The model explains 91.5% of growth variations, indicating strong explanatory power. Based on the findings, this study recommends, among others, that the Nigerian government should implement targeted incentives such as tax holidays, streamlined regulatory approvals, and sector-specific infrastructure investments in non-oil industries to attract FDI, while enhancing domestic absorptive capacity through skills training to mitigate short-run negative effects and maximize technology spillovers for sustained per capita growth.

Keywords: ARDL, GDP *per capita*, trade, FDI, & GFCF.

JEL Codes: O47, O40.

1. INTRODUCTION

The persistence of sluggish per capita income growth in many sub-Saharan African economies has prompted renewed empirical attention to the drivers of growth, particularly how trade openness, capital accumulation, foreign direct investment (FDI), and human capital formation interact to influence real GDP *per capita*. In the case of Nigeria, Africa's most populous economy, this inquiry is especially salient. Although Nigeria is rich in natural resources, growth achievements have often fallen short of transforming living standards, and structural bottlenecks remain endemic. Over the past decades, policy discourse has increasingly emphasized trade liberalization, attracting foreign capital, raising domestic investment, and improving public spending on education as levers for accelerating growth.

Trade openness (measured by total trade as a share of GDP) is theorized to improve allocative efficiency by exposing domestic producers to international competition, expanding market size, facilitating technology transfer, and fostering specialization. Empirical studies in Nigeria from

Abinabo and Abubakar (2023) reported that trade openness has a statistically significant positive impact on growth, controlling for import and export volumes.

Gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), signifying domestic investment in physical capital (machinery, infrastructure, buildings), is central in classical and endogenous growth theories: it expands the productive base, enhances capacity, and complements human capital in raising output per worker. In Nigeria, NBS data show that gross fixed capital formation as a percentage of GDP in the third quarter of 2023 accounted for 12.94 % of real GDP, rising to 15.83 % in the fourth quarter (NBS, 2023). However, empirical estimates of the growth contribution of GFCF in Nigeria using Dynamic Ordinary Least Squares (DOLS) showed gross fixed capital formation exhibited a negative and significant coefficient on growth (Onwiodiokit & Otolorin, 2022).

Foreign direct investment net inflows are posited to strengthen growth by injecting external capital, diffusing technologies, improving managerial practices, and integrating the host country into global production networks. The evidence for Nigeria, however, is mixed. Ayanwale (2007) confirms a positive contribution of FDI to growth, while more recent studies using the period 2010–2019 find that FDI inflows have no statistically significant effect on growth (Ozili, 2024).

Public recurrent spending on education, often proxied as government recurrent (non-capital) expenditure in the education sector, is conceptually a measure of human capital investment: improving schooling quality, supporting operational costs, teacher remuneration, educational inputs, maintenance, and pedagogical materials. The expectation is that higher recurrent spending, appropriately allocated, raises labor productivity, innovation potential, and absorptive capacity, which in turn facilitate sustained growth. Yet, in Nigeria, evidence on this channel is discouraging or ambiguous. For example, Ayaga *et al.* (2024) found that government spending on education has a negative but statistically not significant long-run effect on economic growth in Nigeria.

Despite decades of policy reforms aiming to liberalize trade, attract foreign capital, scale up domestic investment, and allocate more funds to education, Nigeria's trajectory of real GDP *per capita* growth has been disappointingly muted. The key problem motivating this study is the gap between theoretical expectations and empirical realizations: why have the conventional growth drivers failed to generate robust and sustained improvements in living standards in Nigeria?

This study addresses these lacunae by empirically dissecting the causal dynamics of trade openness, FDI inflows, GFCF, and education spending on real GDP *per capita*, offering policy-relevant insights to recalibrate Nigeria's growth paradigm toward diversification and equity.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature

Neoclassical Growth Theory

Solow's (1956) neoclassical growth theory assumes a production function with constant returns to scale, diminishing marginal returns to reproducible (physical) capital, exogenous technological progress and exogenous population growth, competitive markets and full capital mobility; saving–investment determines capital accumulation and transitional dynamics. The Solow–Swan framework implies that gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) raises output per worker in the transition to a higher steady state but that persistent per-capita growth requires exogenous technical progress; empirically, this motivates checking whether Nigeria's GFCF raises real GDP *per capita* only temporarily or has persistent effects once technological change (or its proxies) is accounted for.

Harrod–Domar Growth Model

Harrod (1939) and Domar (1946) assume that fixed capital-output ratios (or strong capital–output proportionality), investment simultaneously creates productive capacity and aggregate demand, and no automatic mechanism ensures the economy stays on a warranted growth path. The Harrod-Domar logic highlights that simple increases in investment (GFCF) can be destabilizing without complementary adjustments (saving behavior, demand management, or effective use of capacity), which helps explain why Nigerian investment spikes need not translate into stable per-capita growth absent institutional and demand-side complementarities.

The Human Capital Theory

Lucas (1988) assumes human capital accumulates through deliberate investment (schooling and learning-by-doing), individual human-capital accumulation exhibits diminishing returns but generates positive externalities (social returns), and markets are imperfect at internalizing these externalities. Lucas’s human-capital externality framework explains why public recurrent education spending might have a large aggregate payoff only when spending translates into widespread productivity externalities (e.g., generalized learning, diffusion), a useful lens for interpreting Nigeria’s weak empirical link between education spending and real GDP *per capita*.

Endogenous Growth Theory

Romer’s (1990) endogenous growth theory assumes ideas/knowledge are nonrival (many can use the same idea without depletion) and partially excludable, R&D and intentional investment endogenously generate technological change, and market structures (monopolistic competition) allow private returns to innovation. Romer’s endogenous-growth perspective implies that FDI and openness matter insofar as they facilitate technology transfer, R&D spillovers, and scale in ideas; for Nigeria, this suggests testing whether FDI and trade openness have growth effects through knowledge diffusion channels rather than only through capital-quantity effects.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Dahal *et al.* (2024) examined the impact of foreign trade and foreign direct investment on Nepal’s long-term economic growth using secondary data from 1989/90 to 2021/22, collected from various economic surveys of the Ministry of Finance of Nepal. Their results showed that exports and imports were negative and statistically significant in explaining Nepal’s economic growth. Similarly, total trade volume and foreign direct investment positively affected economic growth. The study also showed that foreign trade had a multiplier effect on Nepal’s GDP growth. Acharya (2019), using the ARDL method of estimation, found that total trade and foreign direct investment were significant determinants of GDP.

Malefane and Odhiambo (2019) examined the dynamic impact of trade openness on economic growth in Lesotho using the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) bounds testing approach. The study employed four indicators of trade openness, including three trade-based proxies and an index of trade openness. The empirical results showed that trade openness had no significant impact on economic growth in either the short run or the long run, irrespective of which proxy of trade openness was used. Nyomi and Bonga (2018) systematically explored the determinants of economic growth in Nigeria. Their results indicated that the main determinants of economic growth in Nigeria were population growth, inflation, foreign direct investment (FDI), interest rates, exports, and both private and public investment.

Asheghian (2004) examined the determinants of economic growth in the United States over time and investigated whether there was time-series evidence supporting the FDI-led growth

hypothesis. The estimation results suggested that the major determinants of economic growth in the United States were total factor productivity growth, domestic investment growth, and foreign direct investment growth. Tee *et al.* (2017), in their empirical analysis, found that FDI inflows to Ghana were a key driver of economic growth and development.

Gokmen (2021) examined the relationship between net FDI inflows and real GDP for Turkey from 1970 to 2019. The results showed that FDI net inflows did not significantly affect real GDP in the long run. Al-Mutairi *et al.* (2023) investigated factors that impacted economic growth in Kuwait using World Bank and Kuwait Central Statistical Bureau data from 1996 to 2020. The econometric analysis showed that gross fixed capital formation had a significant positive association with economic growth in Kuwait.

Markaj and Haxhimustafa (2024) examined the factors influencing Kosovo's economic growth from 2009 to 2022, specifically investigating the relationships among exports, capital formation, consumption, and economic growth using cointegration analysis and the Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model. Their findings indicated that exports of goods and services, as well as household consumption, negatively affected economic growth, while gross capital formation positively impacted economic growth.

Hashim *et al.* (2018) examined the relationships among five macroeconomic variables: population, gross fixed capital formation, labour force participation, government expenditure on health and education, and real GDP in Malaysia. Their findings revealed that population and gross fixed capital formation were positively related to GDP. Segun (2019) examined whether government expenditure in Nigeria had influenced economic growth. The results indicated that recurrent expenditure exerted a significant positive influence on real GDP, whereas the influence of capital expenditure on real GDP was negative.

Using time-series data and the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model, Christopher *et al.* (2025) examined the impact of government spending on education and health on Nigeria's economic growth. Their results showed that recurrent education spending positively affected GDP per capita, while recurrent health spending negatively affected GDP *per capita* due to inefficiencies. Aninwagu *et al.* (2025) investigated the effects of gendered investment in education on economic growth in Nigeria. Annual data from 1990 to 2023 on government recurrent expenditure on education were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, while data on real GDP *per capita*, female secondary school enrolment, and the Gender Parity Index (GPI) for primary school enrolment were sourced from the World Development Indicators. Their results indicated that government recurrent expenditure on education and female secondary school enrolment positively affected real GDP *per capita*, while the GPI for primary school enrolment had a negative effect.

Nitte (2023) investigated the nexus between economic growth, health, and education expenditure in Nigeria using time-series data for the period 1990–2018. The findings revealed that health and education expenditures were positive determinants of economic growth.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

In this study, research design refers to the systematic plan or blueprint that researchers develop to guide their investigation and data collection process. In this study, the researchers adopted a retrospective research design to investigate the determinants of economic growth in Nigeria.

3.2 Model Specification

The modelling of this study is anchored on endogenous growth. The following models are stated below:

$$RGDP_PC = f(TRADE, FDI_IN, GFCF, GEXP_E) \tag{1}$$

$$RGDP_PC_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 TRADE_t + FDI_IN_t + \beta_3 GFCF_t + GEXP_E_t + \mu_t \tag{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta GDP_PC_t = \alpha_0 & \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^p \alpha_1 \Delta RGDP_PC_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_2 \Delta TRADE_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_3 \Delta FDI_IN_{t-i} \\ & + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_4 \Delta GFCF_{t-i} + \sum_{i=1}^q \alpha_5 \Delta GEXP_E_{t-i} + \lambda_1 RGDP_PC_{t-i} + \lambda_2 TRADE_{t-i} \\ & + \lambda_3 FDI_IN_{t-i} + \lambda_4 GFCF_{t-i} + \lambda_5 GEXP_E_{t-i} + \varepsilon_t \end{aligned}$$

Where;

RGDP_PC = RGDP per capita (2015 Constant price)

TRADE = Total Trade

FDI_IN = Foreign Direct Investment (Net Inflows)

GFCF = Gross Fixed Capital Formation

GEXP_E = Government Recurrent Spending on Education

β_0 = constant parameter or the intercept.

$\beta_1 - \beta_4$ = are coefficients; t = represents time.

Where: α_0 = constant parameter to be estimated; $\alpha_1 - \alpha_5$ = short run parameters; $\lambda_1 - \lambda_5$ = long-run multipliers; p = optimal lag the dependent variables; q = optimal lag of the independent variables; Δ = first difference operator; ε_t & μ_t = error terms.

Note: *RGDP_PC, GFCF, and GEXP_E variables were log-transformed to address scale differences and ensure linearity in the model estimation*

3.3 Data Collection and Methods

The data for the study were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and the World Bank Development Indicators from 1990-2023.

3.4 A priori Expectation

Based on economic theory, it is anticipated that the coefficients β_1 to β_4 will be positive. It is expected that an increase in the variables utilized will positively influence real GDP per capita. Therefore, $\beta_1 > 0$, $\beta_2 > 0$, $\beta_3 > 0$, $\beta_4 > 0$.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The data analysis covered the basic descriptive statistics, unit root, and cointegration tests alongside model estimation and post-estimation tests

Table 1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics for the Variables

	RGDP_PC	TRADE	GFCF	FDI_IN	GEXP_E
Mean	7.588791	15.69147	8.588556	1.294706	4.340677
Median	7.625882	16.23961	8.890338	1.290000	4.850074
Maximum	7.893404	18.04803	11.32526	2.900000	6.624039
Minimum	7.264737	11.95507	5.571279	-0.040000	-1.237874
Std. Dev.	0.235441	1.714396	1.541387	0.843180	1.981637
Skewness	-0.167583	-0.699707	-0.217417	0.169481	-0.989533
Kurtosis	1.349261	2.395607	2.353752	1.889180	3.352476
Jarque-Bera	4.019475	3.291840	0.859514	1.910824	5.724668
Probability	0.134024	0.192835	0.650667	0.384654	0.057135
Sum	258.0189	533.5099	292.0109	44.02000	147.5830
Sum Sq. Dev.	1.829265	96.99212	78.40386	23.46145	129.5872
Observations	34	34	34	34	34

Source: *Researchers' computation using E-views 12.*

The descriptive statistics presented in Table 1 provide an overview of the distributional characteristics of the variables over the study period. The real GDP *per capita* (RGDP_PC) recorded a mean value of 7.588, with fluctuations ranging from a minimum of 7.26 to a maximum of 7.893. The total trade (TRADE) exhibited an average of 15.691, with values spanning from 11.955 to 18.048. Furthermore, the gross fixed capital (GFCF) and the foreign direct investment net inflows (FDI_IN) recorded mean values of 8.588 and 1.294, respectively. The gross fixed capital formation ranged from a minimum of 5.571 to a maximum of 11.325, while the foreign direct investment net inflows fluctuated between -0.040 and 6.624. Similarly, the government recurrent spending on education exhibited a mean of 4.340, with values ranging from -1.237 to 6.624.

The standard deviation results indicate that all the variables display relatively low dispersion around their respective means. This inference is supported by the fact that their standard deviation values are smaller than their corresponding means, suggesting relatively stable series over time.

Finally, the Jarque-Bera statistics associated with the probability values suggest that all variables follow a normal distribution at the 5% level of significance.

4.2.2 Unit Root Test Analysis

In this study, the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) unit root test was employed to determine the stationarity of the time series variable under investigation. The test specification included an individual intercept, and we used the Augmented Dickey-Fuller method, under the null hypothesis that each series possesses a unit root (i.e., is non-stationary).

Table 2: ADF Unit Root Test

Variables	ADF (SIC)				Order of Integration
	Level	5% Critical value	First Difference	5% Critical value	
FDI_IN	-2.389370	-2.954021	-6.971923	-2.957110	1(1)
GEXP_E	-6.137666	-2.960411	NA	NA	1(0)
GFCF	-1.013110	-2.954021	-4.206659	2.957110	1(1)
RGDP_PC	-0.960145	-2.957110	-3.011542	-2.957110	1(1)
TRADE	-2.077092	-2.954021	-6.038803	-2.957110	1(1)

Source: Researchers’ computation using Eviews 12.

Note: The study used a 5% level of significance. An NA sign indicates that the variable is stationary at the level.

The outcomes of the unit root test, presented in Table 2, reveal that only the government recurrent spending on education (GEXP_E) is stationary in its level form. The ADF test statistic for GEXP_E is -6.137666, which exceeds the 5% critical value in absolute terms, implying that the null hypothesis of a unit root is rejected at conventional significance levels. Thus, GEXP_E is integrated of order zero, I(0), and does not require differencing to attain stationarity. In contrast, the remaining variables: foreign direct investment net inflows (FDI_IN), the gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), the real GDP *per capita* (GDP_PC), and the total trade (LOGTRADE) were found to be non-stationary at levels but stationary after first differencing. Specifically, their ADF test statistics are -6.971923, -4.206659, -3.011542, and -6.038803, respectively, all of which exceed the 5% critical threshold in magnitude at the first difference. These findings suggest that FDI_IN, GFCF, RGDP_PC, and TRADE are integrated of order one, I(1), and thus contain a unit root in levels but become stationary in their differenced forms.

Given this mixture of I(0) and I(1) variables, it became appropriate to proceed with a bound testing approach to examine the existence of a long-run equilibrium relationship among the variables.

Table 3: Bounds Cointegration Test Results

Model	K	F-stat	10%		5%		1%	
			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Lower Bound	Upper Bound
RGDP_PC	4	4.824286	2.2	3.09	2.56	3.49	3.29	4.37

Source: Researchers’ computations using Eviews 12

Note: K denotes the number of independent variables

The bounds test results, as presented in Table 3, indicate a statistically significant long-run relationship between the dependent and the independent variables. With an F-statistic of 4.824286, the computed values exceed both the lower and upper bound critical values at the

5% significance level. This provides strong evidence of a long-run relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables in the model.

Model Estimation and Discussion

Table 4: ARDL short and long run results

Short-run results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
D(RGDP_PC(-1))	-0.575730	0.162009	-3.553688	0.0093
D(RGDP_PC(-2))	-0.079185	0.113711	-0.696370	0.5087
D(RGDP_PC(-3))	0.218437	0.095537	2.286406	0.0561
D(TRADE)	-0.049134	0.014477	-3.393897	0.0115
D(TRADE(-1))	-0.084572	0.015478	-5.464168	0.0009
D(TRADE(-2))	-0.047214	0.015964	-2.957530	0.0212
D(FDI_IN)	-0.011212	0.004199	-2.670117	0.0320
D(FDI_IN(-1))	-0.084923	0.014684	-5.783310	0.0007
D(FDI_IN(-2))	-0.045380	0.010220	-4.440233	0.0030
D(GFCF)	0.118020	0.019529	6.043237	0.0005
D(GFCF(-1))	0.052271	0.029367	1.779930	0.1183
D(GFCF(-2))	-0.059278	0.019347	-3.063985	0.0182
D(GFCF(-3))	-0.084666	0.022512	-3.760870	0.0071
D(GEXP_E)	-0.021005	0.009094	-2.309830	0.0542
D(GEXP_E(-1))	-0.039205	0.006711	-5.842240	0.0006
D(GEXP_E(-2))	-0.039356	0.008103	-4.856959	0.0018
D(GEXP_E(-3))	-0.023781	0.009373	-2.537119	0.0388
CointEq(-1)*	-0.620070	0.088025	-7.044234	0.0002
Long run results				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
TRADE	0.055039	0.042227	1.303402	0.2337
FDI_IN	0.109162	0.015128	7.215697	0.0002
GFCF	0.024341	0.045277	0.537601	0.6075
GEXP_E	0.055853	0.032632	1.711583	0.1307
C	6.215936	0.386443	16.08501	0.0000

$R^2 = 0.964812$; $Adj. R^2 = 0.914962$

Source: Researchers' computations using Eviews 12.

Table 4 presents the ARDL bounds testing approach, developed by Pesaran, Shin, and Smith (2001), which is particularly suitable for analysing the determinants of economic growth in Nigeria over the period 1990–2023, as it accommodates variables integrated of order zero or one without requiring pre-testing for unit roots in all cases. In this study, the dependent variable is the real GDP *per capita* (GDP_PC), serving as a proxy for economic growth. The independent variables include the total trade (TRADE), foreign direct investment (net inflows (FDI_IN), the gross fixed capital formation (GFCF), and the government recurrent spending on education (GEXP_E).

In the short run, the lagged dependent variable terms (e.g., $D(RGDP_PC(-1))$ at -0.576, p-value 0.009) indicate persistence in growth deviations, reflecting inertial economic momentum. The coefficient for total trade (TRADE) in the immediate period is negative and significant at -0.049 (t-statistic -3.394, p-value 0.012), with further negative lags (e.g., lags 1 and 2), suggesting that short-run trade shocks, possibly from import surges or export fluctuations, temporarily dampen growth. In contrast, the long run of the total trade (TRADE), yields a positive but statistically not significant coefficient of 0.055 (t-statistic 1.303, p-value 0.233), suggesting that trade openness does not robustly influence *per capita* growth over the long run. This may reflect Nigeria's oil-dependent export structure, where commodity price volatility undermines the gains from trade liberalization, consistent with the resource curse hypothesis (Sachs & Warner, 1995). These findings are consistent with those of Dahal *et al.* (2024) but not Acharya (2019), who found a significant positive effect on real GDP.

Regarding the foreign direct investment net inflows (FDI_IN), the analysis displays consistently significant negative short-run coefficients across lags ($D(FDI_IN)$ at -0.011, p-value 0.032; $D(FDI_IN(-1))$ at -0.085, p-value 0.0007; $D(FDI_IN(-2))$ at -0.045, p-value 0.0030), suggesting initial resource reallocation costs or crowding-out effects that precede long-run benefits, as noted in dynamic FDI models (Alfaro, Chanda, Kalemli-Ozcan, & Sayek, 2004). Conversely, the long-run analysis shows that foreign direct investment net inflows (FDI_IN) have a statistically significant positive coefficient of 0.109 (t-statistic 7.216, p-value 0.0002), indicating that a one-unit increase in FDI inflows is associated with approximately a 10.9% rise in real GDP *per capita* over the long run. This finding underscores the role of FDI as a conduit for technology transfer, managerial expertise, and capital infusion in Nigeria, consistent with the empirical literature on emerging markets, where FDI often complements domestic savings and boosts productivity through spillovers, as theorized by Borensztein, De Gregorio, and Lee (1998). It also aligns with the empirical findings of Tee *et al.* (2017), Nyomi and Bonga (2018), and Asheghian (2004) but contrasts with the findings of Gokmen (2021).

The gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) shows a positive coefficient immediate period effect of 0.118 (t-statistic 6.043, p-value 0.0005) but mixed lagged effects, with negative and significant lags (e.g., lag 3), indicating that immediate capital investments spur growth but face diminishing or reversal effects, possibly due to project delays or maintenance issues (Easterly, 2001). In contrast, the long-run results reveal that the gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) has a non-significant positive coefficient of 0.024 (t-statistic 0.538, p-value 0.608), indicating limited long-run contributions from physical capital accumulation. This could stem from inefficiencies in investment allocation or absorptive capacity constraints in Nigeria's low-institutional-quality environment (North, 1990). These results are consistent with the empirical findings of Hashim *et al.* (2018) and Markaj and Haxhimustafa (2024).

Additionally, the government recurrent spending on education (GEXP_E) displays negative and significant short-run impacts across all lags except in the immediate year (e.g., $D(GEXP_E(-1))$ at -0.039, p-value 0.0006), suggesting that increases in recurrent education spending initially strain fiscal resources without immediate productivity gains, consistent with lagged human capital effects (Lucas, 1988). In the long run, the government recurrent spending on education (GEXP_E) presents a positive but marginally not significant coefficient of 0.056 (t-statistic 1.712, p-value 0.131), hinting at potential human capital effects that fail to reach conventional significance levels. This may be due to measurement issues, such as recurrent expenditures primarily covering salaries rather than quality-enhancing investments, or diminishing returns in an underfunded education system (Barro & Lee, 2013). The positive relationship aligns with those of Aninwagu *et al.* (2025), Nitte (2023), and Christopher *et al.* (2025).

The error correction term, $CointEq(-1)$, with a coefficient of -0.620 (t-statistic -7.044 , p-value 0.0002), indicates that approximately 62% of any deviation from the long-run equilibrium is corrected within one year, suggesting a relatively rapid adjustment speed for a developing economy.

The model's high R-squared (0.965) and adjusted R-squared (0.915) indicate strong explanatory power, suggesting that approximately 91.5% of the variation in $RGDP_PC$ is accounted for by the regressors after adjusting for degrees of freedom.

Residual Diagnostic Tests

Table 5: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test

Null hypothesis: No serial correlation at up to 2 lags

F-statistic	2.584826	Prob. F(2,5)	0.1695
Obs*R-squared	15.25023	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.0005

Source: Authors' computations using Eviews 12

The results of the Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test in Table 5 show a F-statistic value of 2.584826 , with a corresponding probability value (Prob. F) of 0.1695 . Since the p-value exceeds the conventional significance threshold of 0.05 , we fail to reject the null hypothesis of no serial correlation.

Table 6: Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

Null hypothesis: Homoskedasticity

F-statistic	0.302990	Prob. F(22,7)	0.9852
Obs*R-squared	14.63316	Prob. Chi-Square(22)	0.8775
Scaled explained SS	1.122238	Prob. Chi-Square(22)	1.0000

Source: Authors' computations using Eviews 12

The Heteroskedasticity in Table 6 shows a F-statistic value of 0.302990 , with an associated Prob. F of 0.9852 , which is well above the conventional 0.05 significance threshold. The Obs*R-squared statistic is 14.63316 , with a p-value of 0.8775 , while the Scaled Explained Sum of Squares (SS) yields a p-value of 1.0000 . As all p-values exceed 0.05 , we fail to reject the null hypothesis (H_0) of homoskedasticity. This outcome suggests that the residuals exhibit constant variance, indicating the absence of heteroskedasticity. Consequently, the parameter estimates are considered efficient and unbiased, thereby supporting the robustness of the model's inferential results.

Figure 1: Jarque Bera Normality Test

Source: Authors' computations using Eviews 12

The Jarque-Bera test, as presented in Figure 1, assesses whether the residuals follow a normal distribution. The test yields a Jarque-Bera statistic of 4.167617, with a corresponding p-value of 0.124455. Since the p-value exceeds the conventional 0.05 significance threshold, we fail to reject the null hypothesis that the residuals are normally distributed. This supports the statistical reliability and validity of the model's inference framework.

Figure 2: Stability Test

Source: Authors' computations using Eviews 12

The CUSUM plot in Figure 2 demonstrates that the cumulative sum of residuals stays within the 5% significance boundaries throughout the sample period from 1990 to 2023. This indicates no structural breaks in the model, suggesting that the relationship between the determinants of economic growth and economic growth in Nigeria is stable over the analysed period.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

This ARDL analysis of the determinants of economic growth in Nigeria, utilizing time series data from the World Development Indicators (WDI) and Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) spanning 1990 to 2023, reveals nuanced insights into the roles of trade openness, foreign direct investment, capital formation, and education spending in driving real GDP *per capita*. In the long run, foreign direct investment emerges as the sole robust positive driver (coefficient 0.109, $p < 0.01$), underscoring its pivotal function in technology diffusion and productivity enhancement amid Nigeria's resource-dependent economy, while total trade, gross fixed capital formation, and recurrent education spending exhibit positive but statistically not significant effects, potentially masked by structural inefficiencies, volatility, and absorptive capacity constraints. These findings affirm endogenous growth theories emphasizing external inflows and human capital, yet highlight Nigeria-specific impediments such as oil dominance and institutional weaknesses that dilute potential gains. Ultimately, the model substantiates FDI as a cornerstone for sustainable *per capita* growth.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the study makes the following recommendations:

- i. The Nigerian government should implement targeted incentives such as tax holidays, streamlined regulatory approvals, and sector-specific infrastructure investments in non-oil industries to attract FDI, while enhancing domestic absorptive capacity through skills training to mitigate short-run negative effects and maximize technology spillovers for sustained per capita growth.
- ii. Reform trade policies by diversifying exports beyond oil, negotiating balanced trade agreements, and investing in trade facilitation infrastructure like ports and customs digitization to reduce volatility and unlock comparative advantages, thereby fostering stable long-term contributions to GDP per capita.
- iii. The government should focus on public-private partnerships for high-impact infrastructure projects, improve investment allocation through anti-corruption measures and project monitoring, and prioritize maintenance funding to prevent reversals, ensuring physical capital accumulation drives consistent per capita growth.
- iv. Nigerian government should reallocate expenditures from recurrent costs like salaries to outcome-oriented investments such as teacher training, curriculum modernization, and access equity programs, while integrating vocational skills to accelerate human capital formation and yield quicker productivity gains for real GDP per capita.

REFERENCES

- Abinabo, P., & Abubakar, A. (2023). Trade openness and economic growth in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Management Sciences*, 24(2), 217-228.
- Acharya, R. (2019). Foreign trade and economic growth of Nepal: An ARDL approach. *Economic Review of Nepal*, 2(1), 183–201. <https://doi.org/10.3126/ern.v2i1.53133>
- Alfaro, L., Chanda, A., Kalemli-Ozcan, S., & Sayek, S. (2004). FDI and economic growth: The role of local financial markets. *Journal of International Economics*, 64(1), 89–112
- Al-Mutairi, A., Naser, D., Naser, H., & Naser, K. (2023). Determinants of Kuwait economic growth. *Montenegrin Journal of Economics* 19(4), 41-53. <https://doi.org/10.14254/1800-5845/2023.19-4.4>
- Aninwagu, V. O., Amadi, R. C., Onyema, J. I., & Momodu, A. A. (2024). Fiscal deficit and economic growth in Nigeria. *Social Science Review*, 3(2), 215-222.

- Aninwagu, V. O., Odu, G. D., Nyeche, E. (2025). Effects of gendered education investment on economic growth in Nigeria. *Asian Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting*, 25(9), 1-12. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajeba/2025/v25i91951>
- Ashakah, O. F., & Akpughe, W. O. (2021). ECOWAS economic integration and economic growth: Empirical evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of economics and allied research*, 6(2), 1–11.
- Asheghian, P. (2004). Determinants of economic growth in the United States: The role of foreign direct investment. *The International Trade Journal*, 18(1), 63-83. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08853900490277350>
- Ayaga, J. M., & Nomor, D. T., & Obute, C. O. (2024). Government expenditure on education and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Economic and Social Research (JESR)*, 10(1), 185-197. <https://bsum.edu.ng/journals/jesr/vol10n1/files/15.pdf>
- Ayanwale, A. B. (2007). FDI and economic growth: Evidence from Nigeria. *AERC Research Paper* 165. <https://publication.aercafricallibrary.org/server/api/core/bitstreams/11d8c615-17ca-4049-a411-a277ef49c3dc/content>
- Borensztein, E., De-Gregorio, J., & Lee, J. W. (1998). How does foreign direct investment affect economic growth. *Journal of International Economics*, 45(1), 115–135
- Christopher, N., Akpan, M. S., & Ologunla, S. E. (2025). Impact of government spending in education and health sectors on Nigeria's economic growth: A time series analysis of capital and recurrent expenditures. *Journal of Social Sciences and Management Studies*, 4(1), 24–39. <https://doi.org/10.56556/jssms.v4i1.1119>
- Dahal, A. K., Bhattarai, G., & Budhathoki, P. B. (2024). Impact of foreign trade and foreign direct investment on economic growth: Empirical insights from Nepal. *Problems and Perspectives in Management*, 22(1), 390-400 [http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.22\(1\).2024.32](http://dx.doi.org/10.21511/ppm.22(1).2024.32)
- Domar, E. D. (1946). Capital expansion, rate of growth and employment. *Econometrica*, 14(2), 137–147.
- Easterly, W. (2001). *The elusive quest for growth: Economists' adventures and misadventures in the tropics*. MIT Press
- Gokman, O. (2021). The relationship between foreign direct investment and economic growth: A case of Turkey. *International Journal of Economics and Finance*, 13(7), 85-97. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijef.v13n7p85>
- Harrod, R. F. (1939). An essay in dynamic theory. *Economic Journal*, 49(193), 14–33.
- Hashim, E., Romli, N., Ramli, N., & Norasibah, A. (2018). Determinants of real GDP in Malaysia. *The Journal of Social Sciences Special Issue* (3), 97-103. <https://doi.org/10.32861/jssr.spi3.97.103>
- Ikubor, O. J., Oluwaseun, O. A., Saheed, Z. S., & Abraham, A. A. (2022). Government capital expenditure in economic services' sector and economic growth in Nigeria. *Journal of economics and allied research*, 7(2), 296–308.
- Lucas, R. E. (1988). On the mechanics of economic development. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 22(1), 3-42.
- Malefane, M. R., & Odhiambo, N. M. (2021). Trade openness and economic growth: Empirical evidence from Lesotho. *Global Business Review*, 22(5), 1103-1119.
- Markaj, A. K., & Haxhimustafa, S. (2024). Determinants of economic growth in the Republic of Kosovo. *Paradigm Publishing Services*, 19(1). <https://doi.org/10.2478/seeur-2024-0032>
- Momodou, A. A., Amadi, S. N., Nwikina, C. G., & Akosa, I. B. (2025). Impact of exports and foreign direct investment on economic growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economic Research and Development Studies (JERDS)*, 2(1), 216-233.

- National Bureau of Statistics (2023). *Nigerian gross domestic product report (expenditure and income approach)*. https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/pdfuploads/Expenditure_Report_Provisional_Q3Q4_2023.pdf
- Nitte, I. S. (2023). An empirical analysis of the nexus of health care expenditures, education expenditures, and economic growth in Nigeria. *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 9(2), 296-304. <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra12508>
- North, D. C. (1990). *Institutions, institutional change and economic performance*. Cambridge University Press.
- Nyoni, T., & Bonga, W. G. (2018). What determines economic growth in Nigeria. *Dynamic Research Journals (DRJ) Journal of Business & Management*, 1(1), 37-47.
- Onwiodiokit, E. A., & Olorin, G. E. (2022). Capital formation and economic growth in Nigeria: An empirical re-examination. *Bullion*, 45(2), 58-72. <https://dc.cbn.gov.ng/bullion/vol45/iss2/5>
- Ozili, P. K. (2024). Impact of foreign direct investment inflows on economic growth in Nigeria. *MPRA Paper No. 122167*. <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/122167/>
- Pesaran, M. H., Shin, Y., & Smith, R. J. (2001). Bounds testing approaches to the analysis of level relationships. *Journal of Applied Econometrics*, 16(3), 289–326.
- Romer, P. M. (1990). Endogenous technological change. *Journal of Political Economy*, 98(5,2), 71–102.
- Sachs, J. D., & Warner, A. M. (1995). Natural resource abundance and economic growth. *NBER Working Paper No. 5398*. https://www.nber.org/system/files/working_papers/w5398/w5398.pdf
- Segun, A. S. (2019). The rising government expenditure in Nigeria: Any influence on growth? *The European Journal of Applied Economics* 16(2), 95-108. <https://doi.org/10.5937/ejae16-20251>
- Solow, R. M. (1956). A contribution to the theory of economic growth. *Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 70(1), 65–94.
- Tee, E., Larbi, F., & Johnson, R. (2017). The effect of foreign direct investment (FDI) on the Ghanaian economic growth. *Journal of Business and Economic Development*, 2(5), 240-246.
- Wooldridge, J. M. (2013). *Introductory econometrics: A modern approach* (5th ed.). South Western Cengage Learning.